

Shyam Prasad Mukherji Rurban Mission as an Initiative of Indian Government for Rural Areas Development Through Rurbanization

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ABSTRACT

Shyam Prasad Mukherji Rurban Mission scheme was launched by Hon'ble Prime Minister on 21st February, 2016. The Rurban mission has been launched by the Rural Development Ministry which aims to create a cluster of villages and provide urban amenities to the people living within that cluster. Thus, the objective is to create a big village with an urban feel. This will help in improving the quality of life of people in the rural areas and help to reduce the urban-rural divide which will ultimately reduce the rural to urban migration. The clusters should include villages with a population of 25000-50000 in plain areas and 5000-15000 in tribal, hilly and desert areas. These clusters are to be identified by the State Government. The funding of the project will be through various schemes of the Government. The scheme will be implemented through the Public Private Partnership (PPP) model. The Invitation for Expression of Interest from Private Entities to Partner in the Development of Rurban Clusters. Aimed at developing such rural areas by provisioning of economic, social and physical infrastructure facilities. Large parts of rural areas in the country are not stand-alone settlements but part of a cluster of settlements, which are relatively proximate to each other. These clusters typically illustrate potential for growth, have economic drivers and derive locational and competitive advantages. Hence, making a case for concerted policy directives for such clusters. These clusters once developed can then be classified as 'Rurban'.

The vision of "Development of a cluster of villages that preserve and nurture the essence of rural community life with focus on equity and inclusiveness without compromising with the

facilities perceived to be essentially urban in nature, thus creating a cluster of "Rurban Villages".

Keywords: *Entities, Development, Infrastructure, settlements, Inclusiveness, Rurban Villages*

INTRODUCTION

In India, the term Rurban entered the official government literature through the Shyama Prasad Mukherji Rurban Mission (SPMRM) announced in the Union Budget 2014-15. This was following the Rurban development model of urbanization of the rural areas, adopted in the state of Gujarat through which people living in the rural areas are given efficient civic infrastructure and associate services. Ensuring availability of amenities to rural populace is on the top priority of the central government as 69% of India's population resides in villages.

The Shyama Prasad Mukherji Rurban Mission is launched to deliver integrated project based infrastructure in the rural areas, which will also include development of economic activities and skill development. The preferred mode of delivery is through Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) while using various scheme funds for financing.

Government approved the Shyama Prasad Mukherji Rurban Mission (SPMRM) with an outlay of Rs. 5142.08 crores on 16 September 2015. The Mission aims at development of rural growth clusters which have latent potential for growth, in all States and Union Territories (UTs), which would trigger overall development in the region. These clusters would be developed by provisioning of economic activities, developing skills & local entrepreneurship and

providing infrastructure amenities. **The Rurban Mission will thus develop a cluster of Smart Villages.**

Thus, in India, for the purposes of SPMRM, Rurban areas refer to a cluster of 15-20 villages having about 30 to 40 lakh population. The clusters will be geographically contiguous Gram Panchayats with a population of about 25000 to 50000 in plain and coastal areas and a population of 5000 to 15000 in desert, hilly or tribal areas. As far as practicable, clusters of village would follow administrative convergence units of Gram Panchayats. These clusters are intended to be well delineated areas with planned layouts prepared following the planning norms (as laid down in the State, Town and Country Planning Acts/similar Central or State statutes as may be applicable), which would be duly notified by the State/UTs. These plans would be finally integrated with the District Plans/Master Plans as the case may be.

OBJECTIVE

The objective of the Rurbanization is to stimulate local economic development, enhance basic services, and create well planned Rurban clusters. To “develop a cluster of villages that preserve and nurture the essence of rural community life with focus on equity and inclusiveness without compromising with the facilities perceived to be essentially urban in nature, thus creating a cluster of “Rurban villages”.

1. PHYSICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

Strengthening of physical infrastructure by developing inter village road connectivity and mass transport facilities.

2. COMMUNICATION

Provision of electricity, telecom and internet services.

3. KNOWLEDGE

Providing vocational skill development training to the rural youth so that they need not migrate to urban areas in search of jobs. Educational facilities in rural areas will also be upgraded.

4. CIVIC INFRASTRUCTURE

Fully equipped mobile health units, LPG connections, piped water supply, proper waste management, facilities electronic delivery of citizen centric services

and e-gram panchayats are to be provided in these rurban centres.

5. FINANCE

Kiosk banking to promote financial inclusion and provision of cheap loans to the people which will create.

6. HEALTH

Strengthen the PHC (Primary Health Center) and establish mobile health units.

METHODOLOGY

This project seems to be quite ambitious whose success will depend upon various factors. It's too early to say anything. The only thing is that the entire project is to be implemented through PPP mode which has its own shortcomings.

First of all, private sector will have to be encouraged to invest in rural area by giving them Various tax incentives. There should be no bureaucratic hurdles in acquisition of land, environmental clearances etc. which may discourage private investment.

Secondly, the Government will have to balance the profit motive of private sector with the limited income of people in the rural areas while negotiating the contracts.

STUDY AREA

Source: SPMRM

CRITIC

- Model has been taken on national level under PURA which has failed and thus not reliable
- Selection of villages as centre may turn out to be politically motivated and controversial
- Nothing is clear on government's critical gap funding
- States' participation and role is still unclear
- Many argue that it just creates another city which will again lead to more urbanization and emphasis should be on development of every village specifically
- May not be profitable for private sector and they may not participate
- It is required to learn from past mistakes of PURA and sustainable model should be created so that this can be implemented throughout the country.

CONCLUSION

Indian government has unveiled many schemes for the development of the backward regions of India. Shyam Prasad Mukherji Rurban Mission is one such scheme which is for the enhancement of amenities in rural areas with urban facilities. In the past rural areas have been neglected in the wake of industrialization. As most of the manpower stays in rural areas,

effective utilization of the resources can be done through the concept of Rurbanization. Rurbanization has the positives which can cater the needs of rural areas for their development and better growth of the country. As the scheme is initiated, it has to be properly monitored and an administrative lapse has to be minimized so that it can serve the purpose in a better manner.

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